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Automatic vehicle Bangla license plate detection and recognition

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Abstract. Automated license plate recognition is important in many contexts like- security and law enforcement, monitoring vehicles, automated parking control, etc. To enable these automated services in Bangladesh, we are reviewing and combining several established methods in this paper. The task of recognizing vehicle number plates consists of three-stage: plate detection, plate extraction, and character recognition. Each stage has many sub-steps. For every substep, we have reviewed many methods, and chosen the one that proved to be the best solution after thorough testing and observation. The main objective of this research is to gain high accuracy using as little CPU Time as possible, keeping into consideration the facts like- lighting conditions, vehicle motion, noisy plates, segmented words in the input image. The primary target of this thesis is to extract a clean image of license plates of private or community vehicles. Although we target our system to be able to detect standard license plates, we also tested our methods on non-standard plates. We have gained an overall accuracy of 98.41% in plate detection, 82.25% in plate extraction, and 94.11% in character segmentation, resulting in 76.19% overall accuracy using the available dataset. In terms of efficiency, the runtime of our plate detection module is 0.841 seconds, plate extraction is 0.132 seconds, character segmentation required 0.009 seconds, and the average total runtime of the entire system is 0.982 seconds; in our 64-bit machine having 4.00GB main memory and Intel(R) Core (TM) i3-4005U CPU @ 2 × 1.70. In this paper, our aim is to process the input image up to Character Segmentation so that it is easy to recognize the character by sending it to any existing Optical Character Recognition (OCR) system.

Keywords: Digital Image Processing, Automated License Plate Recognition (ALPR), Automated Number Plate Recognition (ANPR), Bangla Number Plate, Number Plate Detection

1 Introduction

In the field of Image processing and computer vision, license plate recognition is a well-established title. It is necessary to create an ANPR system to automate the task of security maintenance, traffic control, parking management system, etc. In Bangladesh, there is only a handful of research on this topic, which promised good accuracy and runtime, but a well-established system is yet to be implemented. Our objective is to find out a way to implement the ALPR system for Bangla license plates, which not only

promises high accuracy but is also an efficient and universal method. In this thesis, we aim to process the input image up to Character Segmentation so that it is easy to recognize the character by sending it to any existing Optical Character Recognition (OCR) system.

An Automated License Plate Recognition(ALPR) system can be divided into several submodules-Plate localization, Plate Extraction, Character Segmentation, and Character Recognition. Plate localization takes any type of input image and outputs the region information of the license plate if available. Plate extraction aims to extract and clean the license plate localized by the previous submodule. Character Segmentation takes the clean plate and separates each character into a separate image. Our objective is to find out a way to implement the ALPR system for Bangla license plates, which not only promises high accuracy but is also an efficient and universal method. There are many challenges to consider during this research. Such as (i) Reviewing and finding the deficiency of previous systems, (ii) Finding a way to implement and test multiple systems, (iii) Building a large dataset of license plate images, (iv) Sorting out the dataset by identifying different types and classes, (v) Measuring the performance and accuracy of our implemented system and how to compare our system to other systems. As there is no established system for license plate detection in Bangladesh, our main motivation is to implement such a system that will be properly usable, as well as complete. This system will greatly help in establishing traffic order in Bangladesh, and provide a strong foundation to successfully apply the laws. Also, the system can be commercialized to the parking lot industries in Bangladesh. But there are many different types in Bangladesh, e.g.: private car, auto-rickshaw, pick up/-van, delivery van/truck, ambulance/mobile dispensary, microbus, articulated truck, micro-bus, etc. Vehicles considered in this thesis are listed in Table 1. There were no previous format and standardization of the license plate. But recently the government has enforced digital license plates for all vehicles.

Table 1: Vehicles class in our consideration (provided by BRTA [1])

Serial	Identifier	Begin Number	End Number	Type
1	MA	51	99	Delivery van/truck
2	THA	11	99	Pick up/van
3	CAA	11	99	Ambulance/Mobile dispensary
4	U	11	99	Cargo truck
5	TA	11	99	Heavy truck
6	GA	11	99	Motor Car
7	RA	11	99	President's office car
8	ZA	11	99	Pm's office (Any vehicle)
9	DHA	61	80	Articulated truck
10	CHA	11	50	Micro-bus
11	PA	11	99	Taxi Cab

License plates also have different colors based on vehicle class. The digital Bengali license plate is normally written in two lines. The line on the top is written in Bangla

and the bottom line has all digits in Bangla. A digital license plate is offering verified fonts, but in Bangladesh, those rules are not strictly followed by all vehicle owners. Also, the current dataset does not have any universal font. So, the fonts can be different but easily understandable for this paperwork.

2 Related work

The rest of the review section will discuss some of the previous works related to licensing plate recognition. The whole task is divided into five main steps: Preprocessing, Feature analysis, Region analysis, Character segmentation, and Recognition.

2.1 Preprocessing

Preprocessing techniques are used to get a better performance in the next sections. This is one of the key tasks after image acquisition. It ensures good data input for the main parts of the license plate detection and recognition system. The most common approach is done in two steps. The image is converted to a grayscale image format for the next steps [5]. Then, any additional noise is reduced from the image with different types of algorithms in different cases. The most common techniques for reducing noise from the input image are the Median filter [6] and the Gaussian filter [7]. Contrast enhancement is an additional technique followed by many researchers [2] in this pre-processing part.

2.2 Feature Analysis

For detecting the license plate, feature analysis must be done after properly preprocessing an image. Checking the edges for detecting any rectangle-shaped area is the most common technique for feature analysis. To detect the plate boundary, some researchers use horizontal lines and others look for vertical lines. Edge detection is commonly done with Canny [8] and Sobel edge detection [9]). As for some exceptions, some researchers do not use edge detection but try to find high contrast areas [10]. The theory behind this technique is - plates generally have a higher contrast area than other parts of the image.

2.3 Region Analysis

When the feature analysis is done, it is possible that several regions of the image can be candidates for the license plate portion. For solving this problem some filtering is needed to lower the number of candidates by analyzing and removing them. A very common technique to do the task is to consider features of the bounding rectangle of the candidate region. For example, we can consider - aspect ratio, size width, height, and location for candidate filtering. For example, calculating the rectangles features for determining the license plate probable region is a common trick [11]. Also [12], [13] and Kong et al. [8] used some geometrical features of the candidate regions to detect

the actual plate region. Following this with further addition of techniques Gazcón, Chesñevar, and Castro [14] proposed that if the region can be divided into well-defined six sub-sections then it is the license plate region. Other researchers like Hung and Hsieh [15] used the geometrical features technique with more or less the same technique by considering characters into the number plate while filtering the candidate regions. A slightly different approach for determining the license plate region was proposed by Chen, Chen, Huang, and Wang [16] by using the high-density edges followed by horizontal projection

2.4 Character Segmentation

Using a histogram to segment the character is a common trick first used by Songke and Yixian and Huang et al. [10]. The technique was to use the accumulation or summation of the vertical and horizontal projections. A connected-component labeling algorithm can be used for character segmentation which was used by Yoon et al. [11] and Maglad [17]. The algorithm acts in two steps. Detection of the connected characters those are in black while the background is white. Then labeling those character blobs with a bounding box. This technique was implemented by Liaqat [18] using two algorithms, Canny for detecting the edges and the contour finding algorithm to find the connected edges. Labeling and segmentation can be done using other methods. The next recognition step used much of the information gained in this step. All this information can be passed to a method for recognizing characters. Tsai et al. [19] tried further judgment of this step to ensure that the selected characters make the actual license plate, not some other part of the image. The conditions to pass this test were that the width and height of character rectangles must be similar, character density should be in a range, and the width must be less than the height.

2.5 Recognition

For license plate recognition there are a few ways to complete the character recognition part. The most common technique can be divided into two steps. At first, the characters from the previous step are provided to a recognition engine that can be coded or used as a package. For example, Open-source Tesseract OCR is a great choice for a character recognition engine. It generates text output from the given image of characters if it is well trained. The second approach is to implement bespoke recognition methods. For each interaction, features are computed. For recognizing the characters, the OCR system will extract features first, then compare them against patterns that have been implemented earlier [20]. Alginahi [21] tried to extract 88 features for each character following the same approach, then compared these features with previously extracted features. Songke and Yixian [6] used a histogram to extract characters and template matching for recognition. Later when the neural network techniques got famous, Ghosh, Sharma, Islam, Biswas, and Akter [22] used them for character recognition. The module is trained first and then used for recognizing characters using the previously given training feature dataset.

3 Methodology

We implemented our solution using Python-3.x using the OpenCV-3 and Numpy libraries from the Anaconda repository. The OpenCV library provides an extensive collection of image processing functions and techniques which proved very helpful in our implementation. Numpy has been used the most to manipulate 2D arrays, and in our design of the Multilayer Perceptron model for recognizing characters. For testing and analysis, we used a separate implementation. In this implementation, we divided entire tasks into a sequence of stages. These stages act like individual modules. For example, a stage for Gaussian filter will only apply Gaussian filter to a set of the input image and save the output to another folder to make it useful as input for later stages. This approach to testing proved to be quite useful and saved a lot of time during our research. The installation and testing process of our implementation is provided in Appendix A.

Figure 1: An overview of the plate detection procedure

We separate our process into several stages. Each stage contains several steps in it. An overview of all stages in our process is shown in Figure 1. Input Image is a 24-bit

colored image with red, green, and blue channels. The plate Detection stage applies several operations on the input image to convert it into an image suitable for feature analysis for later stages. In our case, it also outputs possible locations of the plate and reduces the search space. Plate Extraction analyses all plate-like locations from the previous step, extracts, fixes rotation and cleans the plate for the next module. The character Segmentation step is for splitting the characters from the plate. It is done so that the characters can be recognized by the OCR. Character Recognition uses an OCR system to recognize individual characters and text images.

3.1 Plate Localization

By minimizing the size of an image we can reduce processing time dramatically. But reducing image may result in loss of information. From reviews, we decided to use the dimension: 640×480. We re-scale the input image into this dimension at the first step. From the 24-bit color image, we split the R , G , B components of each pixel (i, j) . Then, the 8-bit gray value is calculated by using the below Equation.

$$\text{gray}(i, j) = 0.11 * B(i, j) + 0.30 \cdot G(i, j) + 0.59 \cdot R(i, j)$$

The vertical Sobel operator is used to calculate the edge density.

$$h = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this step, a 2D Gaussian filter is applied to the gradient image from the previous step. We used a Gaussian kernel of size 60×60. To calculate the kernel the formula in the below Equation is used. Figure 2 shows a plot of this filter.

$$g(i, j) = \frac{a}{2\pi\sigma^2} \cdot e^{-\frac{i^2+j^2}{a^2}}$$

Here, the blur coefficient a and the σ are set empirically. We used *filter2D* function to apply convolution on the gradient image.

Figure 2: The Gaussian filter

3.2 Image Enhancement

We used the Gaussian image to increase the contrast of the image around plate-like regions.

$$I' = f(\rho W_R)(I - I) + I$$

Figure 3 shows the map of the weight function from the Equation. To increase the efficiency of the calculation the entire image is divided into 8×8 windows each having the size of 60×80 . For each window, we calculated weight and mean intensity using Bilinear interpolation. Also by using the NumPy library for matrix manipulation, we could dramatically decrease processing time.

Figure 3: Weight function against normalized edge density

To detect the license plate, the next step is to highlight plate-like regions from the enhanced image. We used a mixture of Gaussian functions that emphasize the constancy of intensity along the horizontal direction within the plate-like regions [4]. The equation shows the mathematical model of this function. This function can properly model low edge densities above, below, and in the middle of the car plate.

A and B are coefficients of the mixture model. We set these parameters by observation and testing, following the condition: $A > 0$ and $B < 0$. The symbol σx is the variance of the main lobe toward x -direction. This filtering process provides a strong response at plate-like regions [4][2]. The result is compared against a threshold value, which is around 80% of the maximum intensity. We call this process smoothing and the threshold value as smoothing cutoff.

This step extracts the license plate and its bounding regions primarily. This does not detect the actual license plate. But gives a close approximation to the location of the license plate. First, we calculated all contours of the image calculated by the mixture model. Next for each contour, we validated the bounding rectangle it is in. If the size of the bounding rectangle is valid, we extract the image of the area and region data.

3.3 Plate Extraction

Here procedure to extract the license plate using the outputs from the pre-processing stage. Before detecting edges we first applied a threshold value to the estimated license plates. Canny Edge Detection is a popular edge detection algorithm. Canny edge detection works perfectly for most cases and provides an easy to detect contours around plate borders [23]. After passing the canny image to the OpenCV's *findContours* function, we get a set of contours. For each of these contours several parameters are checked according to [23] before selecting a contours as a possible plate. The width and height of the detected contour should be above a minimum margin to be recognizable by the OCR. We set the minimum width = 30 pixels and minimum height = 75 pixels for estimated plate. Next we check if the area of the contour is greater than the 10% of the entire image. Remember, we got this image by localizing the plate like regions in pre-processing stage. A possible plate should not have the area below 10% of the entire image. The region information we get from the previous step is used here to extract the plate image from the original image. We also rotate the image to match with the rotation angle found in previous step. This rotation is done by calculating a rotation matrix of scale 1 using a OpenCV. The image from previous stage is need to be converted in binary for convenience. Bangladeshi license plates have two types: white text on black plate for private cars and black text on white plate for public ones. To be accurate, we first converted the image into black and white using two filters: *T HRE SHBIN ARY* one time and *T HRE SHBIN ARYINV* the other. Then compared the ratio of non-zero pixels of each image. The image which has a lesser ratio most probably is selected as the expected binary image. Figure 4 shows the conversion to binary images using the above algorithm for different types of license plates.

Figure 4: Black and white conversion of two types of Image

Removing the borders of an image is a tough job due to the diversity of plates and their origins. In our methods, we first removed the top, bottom, left, and right border using the floodFill function. We checked all the pixels of the first 20 rows and applied flood-fill on any non-black pixels. Similarly, we check the bottom 5 rows, from the left first 12 columns and the right the first 12 columns. Only removing the border is not enough to completely clear the plate image. We used contour analysis to blackout the remaining dots in the image that could not possibly be a letter. To find contour, we used CV_RETR_EXTERNAL mode which only wraps the external area.

3.4 Character Recognition

Character recognition is the final and most crucial part of the automated system. Although we did not implement a system for recognition, we used tested various methods and by following up [4], we formulated simple feature extraction which will be useful in our future work. Although we did not implement it, we provided our design and plan to implement a multilayer feed-forward neural network for character recognition. We have extracted the 27 most basic features that shall help us to identify a character. For each segmented character, we extracted the same amount of features and passed it to the input of the neural network for classification. Our selecting of features effectively reduced the number of computations and made the system more efficient.

3.5 Neural Network Design

A three-layer feed-forward supervised network is designed to suit the purpose. The input layers have 27 neurons, taking the 27 extracted features from the previous step. We used 40 neurons in the output layer because it has 40 different outputs as shown in Table 2. In the hidden layer, we have 180 neurons connecting input and output layers (including bias). Figure 5 shows the network design.

Table 2: The output types of Neural Network

Output type	Count
Bangla Digits	10

Class letters	7
Metropolitan and district words	23

Figure 5: Design of the Neural Network

3.6

4 Experiment and results

Plate Extraction takes every predicted plate and keeps only the text part of the plates. It also removes plates that can't be a possible plate. Canny Edge Algorithm is almost perfect for detecting plate boundary. But if the plate is skewed or angled more than 10 degrees it fails to draw a perfect boundary. In cases where the boundary is not inside the located region, it also fails. Another backdrop is it draws double boundaries for a plate for most of the cases.

Figure 6: Canny edges of a private plate

Horizontal and vertical projects are not perfect for skewed and angled plates. It also fails in case there is induced noise on the license plate. Also if two characters overlap each other in the vertical direction (which is very common in Bangla text) it fails. Figure 7 shows an example of successful segmentation. When two characters overlap the segmentation fails.

Figure 7: Segmented characters from a plate

The overall accuracy of the system shows in the table.

Table 3: Accuracy of our methods

Stage	Total Image	Correct Output	Success Rate (%)
Plate Detection	126	124	98.41
Plate Extraction	124	102	82.25
Character Segmentation	102	96	94.11
Overall	126	96	76.19

5 Conclusion and Future Work

We set our goal to implement a system with high accuracy and efficiency. From the comparison and result analysis, we have surely managed to get a high score in plate localization. But our plate extraction module does not work very well. The primary reason for this is our input dataset. As can be seen, by the statistics from the table, there are lots of variety in the input images. In some of the images, it is very hard to detect and read the characters of the plates even by a human. If we exclude the low resolution and impossible input images, our system works fairly well even for the license plate that was angled or skewed. As we worked through the implementation up to character segmentation, our next goal is to implement a complete system that will recognize the license plate characters given any input image. We could ascertain several other approaches to solve our shortcomings in this research, which we shall test out carefully and select the best method to improve the accuracy of our system. In the future, Optical character recognition is going to be the most challenging part. It is a big field and there exists only a handful of research on this topic for the Bangla language. Among which none are promising enough to provide high performance in terms of accuracy and efficiency. Another way that is in our consideration is using Google's Tesseract OCR, which is open-source and well-maintained. But it requires collecting a good training dataset.

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